

OPINION OF TEENAGERS ON THE IMPACT OF A DIVORCED FAMILY IN MANGALURU

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Abstract

Marriage is a union between individuals, establishing rights and obligations between them and the resulting biological or adopted children and affinity. The provision of breaking this marriage is called a divorce, which may be due to several personal reasons of the parents but it may affect the children born out of this wedlock in many ways that are physical and psychological in nature. This study aims at learning about the impact that a broken family has on a teenager. It also aims at understanding the level of awareness among teenagers about maintaining a healthy family. This study is descriptive in design. The information has been collected using the questionnaire method. The findings are that even though majority of the families do have fights between themselves but not end up in divorces. They spend the quality time with their children. But in the case of the broken family, the children are affected badly both mentally and emotionally even few developed mental illnesses.

Keywords: Divorce, Impact, Teenagers, Broken Family, Marriage, Children, Relationships, Mental Health

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of human society, a **family** is a group of people related either by consanguinity, affinity, or co-residence or some combination of these. Members of the immediate family may include spouses, parents, brothers, sisters, sons, and daughters. Members of the extended family may include grandparents, aunts, uncles, cousins, nephews, nieces, and siblings-in-law. Sometimes these are also considered members of the immediate family, depending on an individual's specific relationship with them.

Marriage is a socially or ritually recognized union between spouses that establishes rights and obligations between those spouses, as well as between them and any resulting biological or adopted children and affinity (in-laws and other family through marriage). When children are born out of this wedlock, it would constitute of a family. Socially, it is such that the parents would take care of their family, that is, their children.

Divorce, also known as **dissolution of marriage**, is the process of terminating a marriage or marital union. It usually entails the canceling or reorganizing of the legal duties and responsibilities of marriage, thus dissolving the bonds of matrimony between a married couple under the rule of law of the particular country or state. Grounds for divorce vary widely from country to country. Marriage may be seen as a contract, a status, or a

combination of these. Where it is seen as a contract, the refusal or inability of one spouse to perform the obligations stipulated in the contract may constitute a ground for divorce for the other spouse. In contrast, in some countries (such as Sweden, Finland, Australia, New Zealand), divorce is purely no fault. Many jurisdictions offer both the option of a *fault* divorce as well as an *at fault* divorce. This is the case, for example, in many US states.

A broken family can negatively affect all domains of the child's development. The effects of a broken family on a child's development depend on numerous factors, including the age of the child at the time of parents' separation, and on the personality and family relationships. Although infants and young children may experience few negative developmental effects, older children and teenagers may experience some problems in their social, emotional and educational functioning. Although this may not always be true, studies suggest that children from divorced families are more likely to exhibit such behavioral issues than those from non-divorced families.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

According to a study by Paul R. Amato, Laura Spencer Loomis, Alan Booth (1995) using a 12-year longitudinal study, they find that the consequences of parental divorce depend on parental marital conflict prior to divorce. In high-conflict families, children have higher levels of well-being as young adults if their parents divorced than if they stayed together. But in low-conflict families, children have higher levels of well-being if their parents stayed together than if they divorced. In marriages that do not end in divorce, parental marital conflict is negatively associated with the well-being of offspring. Franklin, K. M., Janoff-Bulman, R., & Roberts, J. E. (1990) Two studies were conducted to examine the long-term impact of parental divorce on beliefs about the self and others. In Study 1, college-aged children of divorce and students from intact families did not differ on 8 basic assumptions or on measures of depression. Those whose parents had divorced, however, were less optimistic about the success of their own future marriages. Assumptions about the benevolence of people best predicted the marital optimism of the parental divorce group, but not of the intact family group. In Study 2, assumptions about the benevolence of people were explored in terms of trust beliefs. College-aged children of divorce and a matched sample from intact homes differed only on marriage-related beliefs, not on generalized trust. Children of divorce reported less trust of a future spouse and were less optimistic about marriage. Exploratory analyses found that continuous conflict in family of origin adversely affected all levels of trust.

A Government research in the UK had found that Children from broken families are nearly five times more likely to suffer damaging mental troubles than those whose parents stay together. The report was funded by the Department of Health and published by the Office for National Statistics. They investigated emotional disorders - ranked as those which cause considerable distress and interference with the way in which children perform at school and during play. It also looked at conduct disorders which result in aggressive, violent or anti-social behaviour. The researchers studied nearly 8,000 children aged between five and 16 in 2004 and found almost one in ten had disorders. They checked again in the year 2007 and the report says that, a child whose parents had split during this time was more than four and a half times more likely to have developed an emotional disorder than one whose parents stayed together. They were nearly three times more likely to exhibit a conduct disorder. Eleven per cent of those children whose families broke up had emotional disorders, against 3 per cent among those whose families were still together. According to a study conducted by Kobrin and Waite(1986), in the

‘Effects of Childhood Family Structure on the Transition to Marriage.’, the consequences of divorce flow from generation to generation, since the children of divorce are more likely to experience the same problems and pass them on to their own children.

According to Sara S. McLanahan (1988), in her work, ‘Family Structure and Dependency: Early Transitions to Female Household Headship,’ The children of divorced parents are more likely to get pregnant and give birth outside of marriage, especially if the divorce occurred during their mid-teenage years. A study by Arland Thornton (1990), in ‘Influence of the Marital History of Parents on the Marital and Cohabitation Experiences of Children,’ says that divorce appears to result in a reduction of the educational accomplishments of the affected children, weakens their psychological and physical health, and predisposes them to rapid initiation of sexual relationships and higher levels of marital instability and it also raises the probability that they will never marry. According to Amato, a study conducted in 1971 showed 60 divorced families along with 131 children. After five years, two-thirds of the children “were clinically depressed, were doing poorly in school, had difficulty maintaining friendships, [and] experienced chronic problems such as sleep disturbances”. As supported by the study, these children may have started acting aggressive and “engaging in bullying behaviour, both of which can negatively affect peer relationships.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is descriptive in nature and deals with the impact of broken families on the teenagers in Mangaluru, Karnataka. It was conducted on 20 respondents, all of whom are teenagers residing within the boundary of Mangaluru. The tool used for the study is questionnaire and it was administered online to the respondents.

Objectives:

1. To study about the impact of a broken family on a teenager.
2. To assess the awareness among teenagers about maintaining good family relations.
3. To find out the solutions for the probable solutions that can help the teenagers overcome the difficulties that they are going through.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The age groups of the 20 respondents varies from 17-22 with majority of them being in the age of 20. Around 80% of the respondents were female. The respondents are all residents of Mangaluru. Majority of them had educated fathers working as doctors, business men and bankers whereas 70% of their mothers were homemakers. None of the respondents were a single child. The parents of 80% of the respondents are living together whereas of 20% respondents are living separately.

4.1 Parental Fights

It can be seen that the parents of 75% of the respondents fight whereas of 25% do not indulge in fights.

4.2 Quality time

It is evident that 90% of the parent(s) of the respondent do spend quality time with their children by talking to them, going on picnics/vacations, taking them to parks, sharing stories, watching movies etc. Whereas 10% of the respondent believe that the parents are busy with their own work.

4.3 Blaming

From the above pie chart, we can see that 95% of the parents of the respondents do not blame the child for the fights that they have had, at the same time 5% of the parents have blamed the child.

4.4 Walking Out

According to the data acquired, it can be seen that a parent of 80% respondents have not walked out of the family whereas a parent of 20% of the respondents have walked out.

4.5 Friends with Divorced Families

It is evident that 75% of the respondents have had friends with divorced families whereas 25% of the respondents do not have friends with divorced or broken families.

4.6 Link to Mental Illness (Depression, Anxiety etc.)

All the respondents equally agree that broken families can also be a cause to mental illnesses among teenagers such as depression, anxiety etc.

4.7 Effect of walking out

75% of the respondents who have had a parent walk out of their family (20% as illustrated above) said that they felt very bad and were also scared but it made them stronger whereas the rest said that they understood the reason why the parent had to leave and hence it didn't affect much.

4.8 Reasons why families break

According to the responses received, 50% of the respondents believe that marriages break due to lack of respect and misunderstandings. Whereas the other 50% believes that it is due to lack of commitment, falling out of love, communication gaps, incompatibility, lack of trust, having to give up dreams etc.

4.9 Effect on a child

This question received varied responses from the respondents such as the child would feel abandoned and that would isolate them which leads them into depression, they would misbehave, lack self-confidence and self-esteem, lowers morale and tends to repeat the same behaviour in future. Whereas 25% of them seem to believe that this would lead to having trust and commitment issues for the child and losing faith in the institution of marriage.

4.10 Effect on friends

Every respondent who have had a friend hailing from a broken family (75% as mentioned above) says that they were affected very badly by this. They say that it makes them depressed, lonely and tend to blame themselves for what has happened. They tend to have random emotional outbursts and lose self-confidence. They lose faith in relationships and do not trust anyone. Some of them also believe that it may have made them mentally stronger.

4.11 Child ensuring secure family

As individuals, this question had received varied responses such as they could go for counselling, encourage live-in relationships, understanding partners better, conversing and communicating effectively, marrying someone out of their own choice, respectfully handling situations etc.

4.12 Parent ensuring secure family

The respondents believe that the parents should be responsible, patient, love by keeping their egos aside, by living by their vows, instilling family values, communicating effectively, compromising, understanding themselves and family and trusting them, spending more time with each other and providing equal respect.

4.13 Role of Government/NGO in securing families

Majority believe that the role Government and NGOs play are secondary in nature. They could provide counselling and spread awareness about the importance of family and the impact of divorce on the children.

5. MAJOR FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS:

Out of the 20 respondents, all being teenagers, 80% are females. Most of the mothers of the respondents are home makers. 20% of the respondents have parents who live separately. 75% of them have fights in the family. 10% do not have parents who spend quality time with them and only 5% of them have had parents blame them for their fights. 20% of them have had a parent walk out of the family and 75% of them have had friends with divorced families.

100% of them believe that broken families could also be a cause to mental illnesses such as depression, anxiety, etc.

It is important to be seen that even though majority of the families do have fights between them, not all end up in divorces. Arguments usually arise among families and the task lies in handling them. When it is not handled properly or when there is a major mismatch, it results in a broken family.

Even though there are 20% of the parents of respondents who are living separately and have walked out on the family, there is still 90% of parent spending quality time with the child. They spend quality time with their children by talking to them, going on picnics/vacations, taking them to parks, sharing stories, watching movies etc. Whereas 10% of the respondent believe that the parents are busy with their own work.

However, it is the mental impact of the broken family on the child that has to be carefully understood. The ones who have been affected by it and respondents who have had friends who went through it clearly mentions how badly it has affected them. Though it makes them stronger in the long run, it breaks them down emotionally and affects several parts of their lives. They tend to even have mental illnesses such as depression and anxiety to which 100% of the respondents agreed unequivocally.

6. CONCLUSION:

It is detrimental to believe that a broken family can mentally disturb a child. The way it impacts the child's mind are as follows:

1. Health Problems
2. Lack of Self Confidence
3. Irrational Fears and Anxiety
4. Depression
5. Suicidal Thoughts
6. Disrupted Schooling
7. Distrusting Adults
8. Emotional Turmoil
9. Anti-Social Behaviours
10. Losing faith in Relationships
11. Nightmares

It is clear that most of them promote counselling as a therapy not only to the children who are affected by it, but also the parents, the couples who are going through a tough time adjusting among each other. Effective communication can be seen as a way to solve most problems.

There are clearly negative long-term consequences of divorce—children, parents, and society all suffer. Wallerstein's long-term study shows that many children never have full “recovery” as each special event, holiday, or celebration reminds the child of his/her loss. Given these tremendous costs borne by all individuals affected by divorce, as well as the costs to society, it is the responsibility of physicians—especially paediatricians and counsellors, who care for children in the context of their families—to advocate for public health policies that promote marriage and decrease the likelihood of divorce.

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